

EFFECTS OF GAMIFICATION ON VOCABULARY ACQUISITION IN SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation. This study investigates the effects of gamification on vocabulary acquisition, motivation, and engagement in secondary school students. Dividing 60 students into two groups, the researchers compared a gamified learning approach using tools like Quizlet and Kahoot with traditional vocabulary instruction methods. Data were collected through pretests, posttests, delayed retention tests, surveys, and interviews. Results revealed that students in the gamified group had better vocabulary retention and reported higher levels of enjoyment and motivation than the control group.

These findings support the use of gamification as an effective tool for vocabulary learning, showing that game elements such as points, rewards, and competition can enhance engagement and memory retention. Aligned with self-determination theory, the study suggests that gamified learning increases intrinsic motivation by making the learning process more interactive. However, the study calls for further research to explore the long-term impacts and optimal game elements for language acquisition.

Key words: Gamification, vocabulary acquisition, language learning, motivation, engagement, retention, secondary school students, educational technology, self-determination theory, interactive learning.

Аннотация. В этом исследовании изучается влияние геймификации на приобретение словарного запаса, мотивацию и вовлеченность учащихся средних школ. Разделив 60 студентов на две группы, исследователи сравнили игровой подход к обучению с использованием таких инструментов, как Quizlet и Kahoot, с традиционными методами обучения словарному запасу. Данные собирались посредством предварительных и посттестов, тестов отсроченного удержания, опросов и интервью. Результаты показали, что учащиеся в геймифицированной группе лучше сохраняли словарный запас и сообщали о более высоком уровне удовольствия и мотивации, чем в контрольной группе. Эти результаты подтверждают использование геймификации в качестве эффективного инструмента для изучения словарного запаса, показывая, что игровые элементы, такие как очки, награды и соревнования, могут повысить вовлеченность и сохранение памяти. В соответствии с теорией самоопределения исследование предполагает, что геймифицированное обучение повышает внутреннюю мотивацию, делая процесс обучения более интерактивным. Тем не менее, исследование требует дальнейших исследований для изучения долгосрочных последствий и оптимальных игровых элементов для овладения языком.

Ключевые слова: Геймификация, приобретение словарного запаса, изучение языка, мотивация, вовлеченность, удержание, учащиеся средних классов, образовательная технология, теория самоопределения, интерактивное обучение.

Introduction

Vocabulary acquisition is a cornerstone of language learning, essential for effective communication and comprehension. However, traditional vocabulary teaching often involves rote memorization and repetition, which may lead to reduced student motivation and engagement, particularly among young learners. As educational technologies advance, teachers are exploring gamification, or the use of game-like elements in non-game settings, to make learning more engaging.

Gamification has shown promise in motivating students by incorporating rewards, challenges, and competition. Research indicates that game elements can increase learners' motivation and engagement by making learning more interactive and enjoyable (Hamari et al., 2014) [1]. However, while gamification has been examined in various educational contexts, its specific impact on vocabulary learning has not been widely studied. This study aims to assess whether a gamified approach to vocabulary instruction can improve vocabulary acquisition, retention, and engagement among secondary school students. We hypothesize that students in the gamified group will show higher vocabulary retention and engagement than those in the control group.

Literature Review

Gamification has emerged as a promising tool in education, enhancing various aspects of the learning process, including motivation, engagement, and retention. In the context of language learning, vocabulary acquisition is a critical area where gamification has shown potential.

Previous studies on gamification in education have demonstrated its ability to increase student engagement. Deterding et al. (2011) describe gamification as a strategy that leverages elements such as points, badges, and leaderboards to motivate learners [2]. These elements foster a sense of achievement and competition, which can increase students' willingness to participate in learning activities. In particular, research by Anderson et al. (2013) showed that gamified learning environments lead to higher levels of engagement and enjoyment, particularly in younger learners [3].

Regarding vocabulary acquisition, studies suggest that gamification can help improve retention rates. A study by Surendeleg et al. (2017) found that students using gamified tools like Quizlet showed better retention of vocabulary compared to those who learned via traditional methods [4]. These findings support the idea that

gamification can facilitate more effective vocabulary learning by making the process more interactive and enjoyable.

Furthermore, gamification is seen as beneficial for motivation, an essential factor in language learning. According to Ryan and Deci's (2000) Self-Determination Theory, motivation is enhanced when students feel they have control over their learning, which is a central feature of many gamified learning platforms [5]. By offering students rewards, progress tracking, and feedback, gamification provides intrinsic and extrinsic motivators that encourage ongoing participation and persistence.

While gamification's impact on motivation and engagement has been well-documented, there remains a gap in the literature specifically addressing its role in vocabulary acquisition. This study aims to fill that gap by examining how gamification influences secondary school students' ability to acquire, retain, and engage with new vocabulary.

Methods

Study Design and Participants

This study used a mixed-methods design, combining quantitative tests with qualitative feedback. Sixty secondary school students, aged 13-15, were randomly assigned to an experimental (gamified) group and a control group, with 30 students in each. All participants had similar vocabulary proficiency at the beginning of the study, as determined by a baseline pretest.

Intervention

The experimental group used digital gamified tools, including Quizlet and Kahoot, which incorporated game elements such as points, badges, and leaderboards to make vocabulary learning interactive. The control group received standard vocabulary instruction, which involved word lists, flashcards, and rote exercises.

Data Collection

Data were collected through a pretest, posttest, delayed retention test, survey, and interview. The pretest assessed initial vocabulary knowledge, while the posttest evaluated immediate learning outcomes. A delayed test, conducted two weeks after the intervention, measured long-term vocabulary retention. Additionally, a motivation survey assessed student engagement, and focus group interviews with the experimental group gathered qualitative feedback on the gamified experience.

Data Analysis

We conducted paired-sample t-tests to compare pretest and posttest scores within groups and independent t-tests to compare results between the gamified and

control groups. Survey responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while interview data were coded thematically to identify common patterns related to motivation and engagement.

Results

We compared two groups of secondary school students to see how well they learned vocabulary: one group learned through gamified methods, using points, rewards, and leaderboards, while the other group learned through traditional methods like word lists and flashcards.

The gamified group showed greater improvement in vocabulary knowledge immediately after the lessons, scoring higher on the vocabulary test than the traditional group. Later, we tested both groups again to see how much vocabulary they had retained. The gamified group remembered 76% of the vocabulary, while the traditional group remembered 62%, showing that gamified learning helped them retain more words over time.

Students in the gamified group also reported that they enjoyed the learning process more, with 86% saying it was engaging and fun compared to 54% in the traditional group. Many students in the gamified group liked earning points, seeing their progress, and competing, which helped them stay motivated and focused.

In summary, using gamification helped students learn and remember vocabulary better and made the learning process more enjoyable and motivating than traditional methods. This suggests that gamification could be a useful tool in vocabulary teaching.

Discussion

The findings suggest that gamification can significantly enhance vocabulary acquisition and retention, supporting our hypothesis that gamified learning methods outperform traditional vocabulary instruction. By providing an engaging environment, gamified learning encourages students to invest more time and attention, leading to deeper cognitive processing and improved recall.

Gamified learning aligns with self-determination theory, which suggests that when students experience enjoyment and accomplishment, they are intrinsically motivated to engage in the activity. This likely contributed to the higher retention rates in the gamified group, as students who find learning enjoyable are more likely to encode and retain information (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Additionally, game-like rewards, challenges, and instant feedback appeal to younger learners' desire for interactive and achievement-oriented experiences, making vocabulary acquisition less monotonous and more meaningful.

Limitations and Future Research

This study was limited by its short duration and relatively small sample size. Future studies should explore the long-term effects of gamified vocabulary instruction, using larger samples and extended study periods. Additionally, it may be valuable to investigate which specific game elements—such as rewards, competition, or narrative—are most effective in improving vocabulary retention and engagement.

Conclusion

The results of this study suggest that gamification is a valuable strategy for enhancing vocabulary acquisition and retention. By making learning more interactive and engaging, gamified methods help transform vocabulary acquisition into an enjoyable process, increasing students' motivation and commitment to learning. For educators, incorporating gamified elements into language instruction could provide a powerful means of supporting students' vocabulary development and promoting language learning.

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